

Scientific Data Repository-related Policies: Chile

Version 1

**International
Science Council**

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About the World Data System:

Founded in 2008, the [World Data System](#) (WDS) is an affiliated body of the International Science Council (ISC). Its mission is to enhance the capabilities, impact, and sustainability of its member repositories and data services by fostering trusted communities of scientific data repositories. The WDS also aims to strengthen the entire lifecycle of data management, ensuring that high-quality data supports first-class research output. Additionally, it advocates for accessible data along with transparent and reproducible science.

About the WDS series on Scientific Data Repository-related Policies:

The World Data System (WDS) [Policy Series](#) reviews country-specific policies related to the governance of scientific data repositories at the national level. Documenting these policies comprehensively is critical to fostering global collaborations and advancing science for the common good.

To this end, WDS is committed to maintaining and continually updating a list of national Open Science policies pertaining to data repositories. Additionally, WDS will host periodic webinars featuring experts from multiple countries to discuss their unique perspectives on Open Science Policies and how they impact data repositories. These sessions aim to inform researchers and policymakers on how to navigate international policy landscapes effectively.

In developing this Open Science Policy Series, WDS's goal is to create avenues for sharing knowledge and enhancing global scientific collaboration efforts. Ultimately, we hope this approach will promote transparency and ensure that science continues to work towards the common good by leveraging diverse international expertise. Note that the papers in this series will continually be updated with new and emerging information as it becomes available. The World Data System welcomes your input on these documents, including textual updates, references, policy suggestions, and link corrections, by emailing wds-ipo@utk.edu.

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Acronyms

ANID	Agencia Nacional de Investigación y Desarrollo (National Research and Development Agency)
LA Referencia	La Red Latinoamericana para la Ciencia Abierta de Programas (The Latin American Network for Open Science Programs)
CRUCH	Consejo de Rectoras y Rectores de Universidades Chilenas (Council of Rectors of Chilean Universities)
CUP	Corporación de Universidades Privadas (Corporation of Private Universities)
INA	Infraestructura Nacional de Acceso a la Información Científica (National Infrastructure for Access to Scientific Information)
CINCEL	Consortio para el acceso a la información científica electrónica (Consortium for Access to Electronic Scientific Information)
InES	Innovación para la Educación Superior (Innovation for Higher Education)
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable & Reusable

Introduction

This document compiles the policies and documents related to scientific data repositories in Chile. It provides links and brief explanations that facilitate their consultation by researchers, managers, and decision-makers interested in Open Science.

In recent years, Chile has developed various initiatives related to the management and policies on scientific data repositories, mainly promoted by government agencies and universities. In 2022, the National Agency for Research and Development (ANID) implemented the Policy on Open Access to Scientific Information and Publicly Funded Research Data, which establishes the obligation to deposit publications and data derived from publicly funded projects in open-access repositories. However, its adoption and effective compliance face challenges at the cultural, institutional, technical, and financial levels.

Along with the above, an absence of clear operational guidelines, disparate institutional technical capacities, and a lack of systematic follow-up resulted in some institutions taking the initiative autonomously in the context of the execution of InES Open Science projects. Such is the case of the Universidad Central de Chile, which in 2023 prepared and published a detailed technical document for its institutional repository to facilitate the interoperability of its content with other platforms (Universidad Central de Chile, 2023). This document includes mapping between metadata schemas such as Dublin Core, DataCite, and OpenAIRE, as well as local fields, in anticipation of the official ANID document, published in 2024.

At the same time, various higher education institutions made progress in the formulation of specific institutional policies to strengthen the management of and access to scientific data generated by their researchers. Of particular note are the policies published within the framework of the InES Open Science projects by the Universidad Central de Chile (2023), the Universidad del Desarrollo (2023), and the Universidad Católica de la Santísima Concepción (2023), which have established internal guidelines that promote open practices for the management, preservation, and reuse of scientific data. However, there is still a need to integrate the valuation, recognition, and financing for those who adopt these practices, especially concerning the training and sustainability of the advanced human capital that sustains them.

The national context has also been influenced by regional initiatives such as LA Referencia, a network of which Chile is a founding member and node through ANID. This participation has contributed to the strengthening of the regional infrastructure for the interoperability of repositories and open access to scientific information, generating the challenge of moving towards an articulated national governance of the scientific data system.

Also noteworthy is the publication of the proposed Strategy for the Implementation of a FAIR Data Policy in Chile (Abedrapo et al., 2025), the product of the project led by the University of Notre Dame and the Lucy Family Institute, in collaboration with the Data Observatory Foundation, Universidad Central de Chile, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile,

Universidad de los Andes and Chilean individual researchers, and the support of the international initiative GO FAIR. This document outlines a national roadmap to overcome gaps in governance, infrastructure, capacity building, and institutional culture, aligning the country's efforts with global standards in open science. The proposal seeks to strengthen the national ecosystem of open, ethical, and interoperable scientific data, positioning Chile as a regional benchmark in data governance.

One of the main coordination mechanisms at the national level has been the National Infrastructure for Access to Scientific Information (INA), led by ANID together with the CINCEL Corporation, conceived as a public-private network with the participation of CRUCH and CUP, with objectives of balanced representativeness in terms of participation of the various actors of this system and transparency of its actions for the entire community related to the generation of knowledge. However, its surveys and other documents generated are not publicly accessible, which also presents a challenge with respect to transparency and coherence with the principles of openness, participation, and accountability, which the initiative itself claims to promote.

In this context, the document Metadata Guidelines and Interoperability Mechanisms (ANID, 2024), associated with the national node of LA Referencia and published in January 2024, is seen as a starting point towards such a need, but does not incorporate the initiatives previously developed by the various higher education and research institutions.

Policies Related to Scientific Data Repositories

Chile-specific policies related to scientific data repositories include:

National Policies

1. Open Access to Scientific Information and Publicly Funded Research Data Policy (ANID, 2022)

Implemented by the National Agency for Research and Development (ANID), this policy establishes that the results of publicly funded research must be deposited in open-access repositories. Its implementation is progressive and seeks to ensure the availability of scientific knowledge for the society as a whole.

Complementary technical instruments

2. Metadata Guidelines and Interoperability Mechanisms for Institutional Repositories (ANID, 2024)

Technical document prepared by ANID as part of the National Access Node. It defines metadata schemes, minimum fields, and standards to facilitate interoperability between institutional repositories and their articulation with LA Referencia. Its application is directly linked to the technical implementation of scientific data repositories at the national level.

3. Strategy for the Implementation of a FAIR Data Policy in Chile (Abedrapo et al., 2025)

It proposes guidelines to strengthen the adoption of the FAIR principles in the national scientific data ecosystem, addressing the need for a strategy that considers governance, infrastructure, technical capacities, regulatory framework, and institutional culture on data. Including considering and valuing the formation of human capital, the development of interoperable repositories, and the implementation of a national GO FAIR office.

Institutional Policies

4. Open Science Policy of the Universidad Central de Chile (2023)

It promotes open science practices in all aspects of research, including the management, preservation, and open access to the data generated. This policy seeks to improve the quality of research, promote transparency, and facilitate access to knowledge.

5. Open Science Policy of the Universidad del Desarrollo (2023)

It establishes guidelines for managing the scientific data generated by its university community, promoting its deposit in institutional repositories and the use of persistent identifiers. The policy also emphasizes training in open science and the integration of these practices in the evaluation of research projects.

6. Institutional Policy of Open Science of the Universidad Católica de la Santísima Concepción (2023)

It regulates the management of data and scientific results to facilitate their access, preservation, and reuse, being a pioneer in the implementation of Open Science policies in Chile.

7. Regulations on Open Access and Research Data Management of the Universidad de Santiago de Chile (2025)

It promotes open access to scientific publications, encouraging their deposit in the institutional repository or open-access platforms, and establishes guidelines for the management of research data.

8. Open Access Policy of the Universidad Autónoma de Chile (2025)

It establishes guidelines for the deposit of publications and research data in institutional repositories, promoting the free circulation of knowledge generated with public funding.

It should be noted that, although many universities that were awarded Open Science InES projects set the objective of creating policies or governance documents, in several cases these policies have not been finalized or are not publicly available, such as the Universidad de Atacama and the Universidad Católica del Norte, who announced the institutional approval of their respective open access and open science policies.

Complementary research: FAIR alignment of Chilean repositories

In line with this review, the authors are developing an article that evaluates the level of alignment with the FAIR principles of the repositories implemented in the framework of the InES Open Science projects, together with the ANID repository. The study is based on an open dataset that documents the characteristics of 30 institutional repositories (Abedrapo, Martínez & Hartley, 2025), including the type of content, software used, use of persistent identifiers, metadata schemes, presence of local and gender fields, and availability of documentation. This analysis will allow the characterization of the quality, interoperability, and openness of the national infrastructure for scientific data in Chile.

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